

Failure Detection Methods to Predict Loss of Control Involving Human-Interface Devices Part II: Empirical Validation¹

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Abstract

A companion paper [1] has addressed certain theoretical issues concerning the design of a human-interface device to help predict the loss of tracking control when a human operator is involved in a position tracking scenario. This Part II paper will describe the empirical validation of such a system with human subjects within a laboratory scenario. Such an apparatus can be used to help mitigate the loss of control by giving the operator a warning *a priori* or possibly used to adapt a display or controller (adjust the automation level).

1. Introduction

Figure (1) illustrates a block diagram description of a human-machine interaction involving position tracking. A detector type device has been described in [1] which can help the operator to detect the potential loss of control of the tracking task. Figure (2) illustrates its operation in which estimates of the closed-loop tracking error and its higher derivatives are computed via a method such as a low-pass filter model. Figure (3) illustrates a US Air Force subject involved in an experimental tracking paradigm to be described in the sequel. When controlling a task of this nature, the characteristics of the closed-loop tracking error capture the essence of whether the overall system is in a mode of operation which can be classified as controllable or non-controllable. Figure (4) illustrates the tracking error versus time with notations on when tracking divergence occurs as well as the possible incidence of PIO behavior. PIO (Pilot Induced Oscillation) is a phenomenon that occurs at the brink of instability of a human-machine system. Studying the human-machine system within a PIO context is extremely important because the sensitivity of the interface to all design parameters is significantly enhanced at this point. An experimental scenario to induce a PIO or loss of control situation is now described so as to provide a framework to investigate the detector design as well as

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potentially other variables that could be used to improve the human-machine interaction.

2. The Experimental Scenario to Study the Human-Machine System at Instability

At the Air Force Research Laboratory, Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio, studies are on-going to develop assistive systems (adaptive joystick controllers or displays) that may accommodate when particular situations may arise. The potential loss of control or PIO is a critically important situation to study. If a detector can estimate this untoward event, then, perhaps, the display or controller may be adjusted to help prevent a crash or other undesirable event. To replicate a situation likely to cause a loss of control, four experimental variables were manipulated in a laboratory experiment. They include:

- (1) A time delay was introduced between the stick output and the effect it produces on the aircraft dynamics under control by the operator (f_p) in Figure (1).
- (2) A force-reflecting joystick versus a non-force-reflecting joystick was employed. Certain paradigms of this type are known to enhance tracking performance (cf. [2,3]).
- (3) High and low noise turbulence on the roll axis were included. These high turbulence conditions are known to help trigger a PIO in the presence of a large time delay in the pilot-vehicle loop.
- (4) High and low noise turbulence on the pitch axis of the pursuer aircraft was also an experimental variable.

Such an experimental design is termed a Latin Square design of type 2^4 with four independent variables. Seven subjects ran a total of eight data days with 16 trials per day of the experimental conditions presented in random order. Both objective and subjective data were collected. The subjective data included Cooper-Harper ratings of the task and a PIO questionnaire [4]. The subjective data were necessary to provide concurrence with the objective data to help make a determination of an actual loss of control or oscillatory behavior.

Training of subjects was accomplished by gradually increasing the time delay and intensity of the noise turbulence variables until oscillation and/or loss of

tracking control was evident. The 16 daily trials consisted of low and high values of the four stressors presented in randomized order.

3. The $\gamma(t)$ Metric of the Detector

With reference to [1], a metric to evaluate the potential of tracking divergence is predicated on a variable defined as follows:

$$\gamma(t) = r_1 + r_2 + r_3 \quad (1)$$

where:

$$r_1 = n_1/Nx \quad (2)$$

$$r_2 = n_2/Nx \quad (3)$$

$$r_3 = n_3/Nx \quad (4)$$

and Nx is the total number of data samples under consideration (sliding window) and n_1 , n_2 and n_3 of these data samples fall in quadrants I and III of specially constructed phase-plane portraits [1] of the closed-loop error signal. The position tracking error signal is first measured and the higher order derivatives estimated via a numerical filtering routine. It is shown in [1] that large values of $\gamma(t)$ can be correlated with tracking divergence and, in particular, a threshold exists in which a decision rule, based on a threshold value, can be used to make a determination of the loss of control. One such possible rule would be:

- (a) $\gamma(t)$ must be greater than some threshold value, e.g. $\gamma(t) > 2.0$ for tracking divergence to be precipitated. (5a)
- (b) The rate of change of $\gamma(t)$ must be positive prior to the loss of control. (5b)

This paper will investigate the values of a threshold value such as 2.0 in equation (5a) and the possible types of transgressions introduced by this decision rule.

4. Results from the Data

Figure (4) illustrates not only $e(t)$, the actual data from a run, but also $\hat{e}(t)$, a low-pass filtered estimate of this variable. If $|e(t)| > 3000$, the target aircraft is off the screen and the subject has failed at the task. Thus the magnitude of $e(t)$ defines failure, as well as the properties of $\gamma(t)$. The data presented here were analyzed across seven subjects who were paid for their participation in this study.

5. Statistical Analysis of the Independent Variables

From the subjective data (Cooper-Harper (C-H) ratings and PIO ratings) as well as from objective measures (magnitude of the tracking error, crashes, etc.), it was necessary to demonstrate that the subjects were sufficiently stressed to lose control of the tracking task as a consequence of the independent variables selected in this experiment. A complete ANOVA (analysis of variance)

was conducted across subjects in terms of the independent variables that affected their behavior. Table I illustrates the effect of each of the independent variables on tracking considered to be in a controllable mode versus runs that indicated tracking behavior that was not controllable. F connotes F ratio, τ is the delay variable, and p is the level of statistical significance.

Table I - Effect of The Independent Variables

C-H Ratings	$\tau = .179$ s	$\tau = .763$ s	$F = 6.88$	$p < .0001$
Roll Noise	$Rn = 2$	$Rn = 7$	$F = 0.46$	$p = 0.646$
Pitch Noise	$Pn = 2$	$Pn = 7$	$F = 3.36$	$p = 0.0064$
Force On/Off	Force on	Force off	$F = 5.64$	$p = .002$

A second analysis was conducted to evaluate the efficacy of a decision rule in a post hoc sense on data already collected, which leads to a caveat on the procedure.

Caveat

As with any decision mechanism, there exist missed negatives and false positives (Type I and Type II error). Using a decision threshold, as in equation (5a), the detector was first applied to tracking data in which it was known that the subject either was in control or lost the target. This was verified by both objective and subjective measures. Using a decision rule based on a fixed threshold, the number of false positives and missed negatives was determined. These events were calculated when the detector made a decision which was or was not at variance to the actual event. Two independent variables were considered in this second analysis. It was felt that the bandwidth of the low-pass filter (α) which generated the higher order derivatives that provided the input to the detector and the length of the window of time samples (Nx) would certainly bias the results. Data were analyzed within a subject, and figure (5) illustrates a MATLAB plot of the number of false positives (Fp) and missed negatives (Mn) versus the two independent variables α and Nx for a fixed decision rule. It is clear that, for choices of $\alpha > 15$ radians/second and $Nx > 35$ samples (20 Hz was the sampling rate), the missed negatives and false positives could be reduced to levels that were considered negligible.

6. Summary and Conclusions

An empirical validation of a tracking error detector was conducted using an experimental paradigm designed to produce a loss of control or pilot induced oscillation. The detector was evaluated for a fixed threshold level and applied in a post hoc sense on data. With a sufficiently high bandwidth of the low-pass filter to generate the phase-plane portraits, and for a sliding

window of data of a few seconds, the missed negatives and false positives of the detector could be reduced to inconsequentially small values.

7. References

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Figure 1 - The Human-Machine Interaction System

Figure 2 - Detector System in Operation

Figure (3) - Subject in Critical Task (PIO) Experiment

Figure (4) - Closed-Loop Tracking Error

Figure (5) False Positives and Missed Negatives Versus alpha and Nx - Sliding Window Length

Fp and Mn average plot for LSH

